

The Incredible Experience of Being Nina Thornhill's PhD Student

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Abstract: How do you find a good PhD supervisor? It is not an easy task. After all, even experienced people tend to only have done one PhD and therefore don't have a comparison. Also, you cannot underestimate the role of a supervisor. In German, this is expressed in the word for PhD supervisor: 'Doktorvater' – doctor father. I think of Nina as my 'Doktormutter' and it couldn't be more descriptive. You can agonize over the question of finding a good supervisor, do intensive research, but at the end of the day you have to have bit of luck to find the best.

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1. UCL – ERASMUS EXCHANGE 1998

When I decided to embark on an Erasmus exchange to England in 1998, there was an existing relationship between my university and University College London (UCL). I had enjoyed signal processing in the first two years of my degree and contacted the lecturer to ask if I could do a project with him. Luckily, he never answered. I looked further into the electrical engineering department and found descriptions of control projects that sounded interesting. I emailed the lecturer and – of course she emailed back immediately, because it was Nina.

In the following year I sat in a UCL lab just off Torrington Place in Central London with a little hotplate and beaker, watching water and vinegar boil. I recorded the noise that the boiling process made with a little, cheap microphone. More often than not did I record the infernal racket of the sledgehammer at the next-door building site and the rumble of the red double-decker buses passing by in the street. It was great fun.

I was enthralled, not only with the magical melting pot of different cultures that London is, but also with the English academic system, so different to the German universities. In Germany, I had experienced ancient looking professors reading their own textbooks from overhead projector slides to a near empty auditorium that could seat 500. We students were in the meantime recovering from the previous weekend of drinking Frankonian beer and studying the textbooks on our own.

At UCL, I heard Nina lecture Control Systems and I was astounded. First she introduced herself as 'Nina'. 'Nina? We can't call you that? You're the lecturer!' Even my fellow British students were surprised. She went on to explain control in a way we all felt we understood only by listening to her lecture. Every sentence made sense. The impression that control systems would be easy was obviously not true. Control systems anything but easy. But it was the first time that attending a lecture was worth every minute. I was in love with control from the very first day.

2. UCL – PhD 2002 TO 2005

After the year in London I completed my degree and shortly thereafter started working in the sales and marketing department of a large semiconductor company. To those who are not aware of this: A key requisite of a sales person is to not tell the truth outright. Ideally, you are blessed with a poker face. Unfortunately, I have never learnt the skill of controlling my facial muscles so that they do not display my raw emotions; a genetic or learnt flaw to which I'll return. Needless to say I was entirely unsuited for the job.

When I emailed Nina saying that I was quite miserable and asked her if could do a PhD with her she replied that she would not take me on as a student without funding. She felt that a self-funded student would not be able to sustain a PhD over a period of three years and would eventually abandon the PhD for a paid job. What Nina did offer was to help me apply for what she called a 'Mercedes', the UCL graduate scholarship that would cover all fees and living expenses. In hindsight, this was exactly the right strategy.

Back at Torrington Place in the Mercedes and after a difficult personal time, Nina received me with a huge hug and I knew I had made the right decision. She had remembered the names of all of my classmates from my Erasmus year – my friends Marvin Govinden, Polo Tang and Nishita Hathi, who had all by then embarked on their own, successful careers. Nina remembered their names because she truly cares about people.

The Head of Department at UCL at the time was a sweet English gentlemen and engineer of ample girth and with great ambition. I remember finishing a conversation with Nina. She walked away down the corridor, right past the HoD, whom she greeted, towards the cleaning lady. She had helped the lady on a previous occasion and was following up on the issue. The expression on the face of the HoD of utter confusion is etched in my mind. Never before had he been treated with the same, or possibly slightly less respect as a cleaning lady. He was baffled, Nina, who couldn't see his expressions, was completely oblivious to what she had just done.

3. ON LISTENING

It has always been easy to underestimate Nina. Possibly because Nina is woman in a male dominated engineering discipline but also because she is generally quiet and calm. She never shows off or talks about her achievements. Her excellence in thought and experience quickly becomes evident though when she sits in an audience and afterwards asks the sharpest questions that make the presenter rethink their entire approach.

Nina will listen attentively to any presentation, showing her support of all new and inexperienced PhD students with a smile. I myself have the terrible habit of showing my emotions through my facial expression. When I attended my very first large conference, the ECC in Cambridge in 2003, the plenary presenter was giving a talk on stability analysis of discrete-time systems by saturation dependent Lyapunov function. I was shocked when he stopped in his, pointed at me, sitting somewhere in the middle of the fully packed auditorium. "You! Yes, you! Why are you looking so perplexed?!" You can imagine what impact 'that look' has in a small room on a nervous presenter. My husband tells me it is not pretty. Since that day I make a conscious effort, whenever I notice that I'm puzzled about a presentation, to try and put on Nina's look of interested, encouraging serenity.

During those years I witnessed strong attacks of angry professors reprimanding students after their presentations for making stupid mistakes, not understanding the subject, repeating work that had been done 40 years ago ("If you read my paper from 1967..."). Academics did this in no mistaken terms and often using uncompromising language. In recent years, I have noticed that often there are fewer or no comments from the audience and shouting matches seem to be a thing of the past. This is somehow worse than angry professors. But I wish we could all listen to presentations like Nina, encouragingly, asking questions that change the presenter's perspective.

4. BP CHEMICALS

After I had completed the initial literature study I needed industrial data to try out first ideas. Nina arranged a day visit to BP Chemicals in Sunbury, outside London, where Adrian Meaburn would supply us with data. I felt out of my depth for many reasons – venturing out of central London meant that I could no longer blend in among the international crowd. My German accent was rather pronounced at the time and I was scared that people would ask me about Hitler and the war, as they had done on previous occasions when I had ventured into England.

I was relieved when, after arriving at the office building, I successfully passed the safety drill and subsequent exam that tested your knowledge of the emergency exits as well as your ability to – safely and hypothetically – climb a staircase in an office building while carrying two bags (you leave one bag at the bottom of the steps, carry one bag up and return to fetch the other).

Nina clearly enjoyed the trust and admiration of the BP colleagues. She led the discussion that – to my horror – was

conducted in a different language. I understood absolutely nothing. What was P-N-I-D? Or a rectification column? My ears pricked up when I heard a familiar term: High frequency data. Now frequency was something I new all about, being an electrical engineer. But a sampling rate of once per second? That surely couldn't be high frequency? Nothing made sense.

A few weeks after the visit, Nina, who had observed my shortcomings, suggested that I'd attended courses at the chemical engineering department and possibly even pursue a Master's degree there. I didn't take the advice. I raced through the PhD as quickly as possible, finishing in two and half year to move to South Africa for a man. How foolish. Had I known I was going to spend my life with him I would have realized there was no need to rush.

Today I know what rectification columns are and that P&ID stands for piping and instrumentation diagram but I still often have to muddle through when I speak to process engineers. I get thoroughly intimidated. I wish I had taken Nina's advice and learnt the fundamentals of process engineering properly when I had the time and freedom.

5. CANADA

An envious colleague from the business unit at ABB once complained to me that academic conferences really should be called 'scientific tourism'. I couldn't agree more. Travelling to a conference with Nina, as her PhD student was like going on a five star holiday with your best friend.

One of my first international conferences was an IEEE Workshop in Vancouver in 2004. This event was made memorable to all participants by a distinguished university professor from the Netherlands who dropped the following sentence in his keynote: 'Simulation is like masturbation: if you do it to often you think it's the real thing.' A bombshell. The largely Canadian audience reacted with stunned silence. Nina, managed to stifle one of her quiet chuckles, while I, embarrassingly, was the only one who burst out laughing.

During the following break I chatted to another PhD student. He was sharing his room with a classmate in a cheap B&B at the other end of town. I was enraged – how could the professor stay in the upmarket conference hotel while the students had to rough it up? Only years later did I understand that I, or rather Nina, was the exception. She always made sure her student was on the same convenient flight as her, stayed at the conference hotel and had all the requisites for a successful scientific experience that would motivate you to work harder for the next event.

My experience of conferences was warped further, because all events I attended then had a dance floor as part of the banquet. Every workshop, conference or symposium I have attended since, which didn't have an opportunity to express yourself through physical movement, has been a huge disappointment. And the dance floor was made for Nina. While us students were exhausted from jetlag and long days full of presentations, Nina took to it and got the party started. It was a sheer joy to watch and join in. During those nights I found out about her great affinity to heavy metal music. Who would have thought?

Nina had spent many months in Canada previously, privately and professionally. In 2001, she had undertaken a one-year sabbatical in Edmonton at the University of Alberta. During our two weeks visit in 2004, she introduced me to her very good colleagues Sirish Shah, Shoukat Choudhury and Biao Huang as follows: 'This is my friend Margret'. To this point I had only known of these brilliant minds from reading their papers and admired them greatly. Nina went on to give invited lectures at the University of British Columbia and the University of Alberta and took me with her. She made sure I gave part of the presentation, treating me as an equal from all perspectives. I was in the second year of my PhD and I felt on top of the world.

5. EASTMAN CHEMICAL COMPANY, TENNESSEE

After two years I had developed methods that in first applications to BP data seemed promising. While researching these methods, I had studied many papers that used what is known as the 'Tennessee Eastman Challenge Process'. The authors, Jim Downs and Ernie Vogel at Eastman Chemical Company had taken an actual chemical process, which was located in Kingsport, Tennessee, and described all dynamics in differential equations. The resulting simulation model – originally intended as an operator training tool – was given to the academic community where it was snapped up and incorporated into many research projects.

Influenced by Nina's guidance and by the advice given by the distinguished university professor from the Netherlands at the conference in Vancouver, I wanted to apply my methods to real industrial, not simulated data. Nina arranged for me to stay for two months of my PhD at Eastman Chemical Company in Kingsport, Tennessee, where I would spend time within the Advanced Control group to gather example problems and data. I couldn't believe it – to me this was what for others would be going on tour with rock stars.

Nina accompanied me to Kingsport in July 2004, where she gave a presentation and discussed further research projects and problems that the group had encountered. I didn't know what Tennessee would look like – after all this was before Google Earth. I pictured large, open savannah and rocks like on pictures of Death Valley. Not the lush jungle of the Great Smokey Mountains, which Nina and I explored in the few days that she spent there at the beginning of my stay. Together we visited the largest, privately owned house, the very grand Biltmore Estate, and hiked in the Cherokee National Park.

Then I was left to fend for myself. I quickly learnt that Tennessee is on a different buzz compared to the English countryside. I found this out the hard way when I ventured out on walks from the complex where I stayed. It's in the DNA of a German to go out walking and hiking wherever we travel. On my first walk through the nature of the neighbourhood I was accosted by a shotgun-wielding homeowner who threatened to shoot me for trespassing onto his property. The second time I ended up in a hedge full of angry bees, which followed me all the way back to the complex from where I rushed off to the Walmart pharmacy to attend to my wounds. There was no third time.

After that, Jim and his colleagues John Cox, Michelle Caveness, Steve Miller and Chip Anderson took great care of me, inviting me to their homes. I was made part of a baby shower, a family barbeque and was invited to a Sunday service at the Baptist church, which might have been a mosque or temple, so different was the experience. Needless to say, I learnt more by being on a chemical site than what I could ever have sitting in the office in the centre of London. Nina of course knew that.

6. ABB CORPORATE RESEARCH

ABB struck gold when they hauled Nina into the corporate research organisation. After years of successful collaboration with ABB Norway, Italy and Germany, a very smart move by then CTO Peter Terwiesch was to set up the ABB/Royal Academy of Engineering Professor of Process Automation. Instrumental in his support was Alexander Horch. Alexander was the manager of the research project that took many of Nina's methods, together with one of mine, and incorporated them into a software tool. This tool analysed plant-wide disturbances, a novelty world-wide.

It was Alexander who recruited me into ABB Corporate Research Centre in Germany (DECRC) while I was doing my postdoc at the University of Pretoria. I remember standing outside a lagoon of the St. Lucia wetlands in South Africa, observing hippos sticking their heads above the water, coming up for air. I had met Alexander a year previously at a CPSE meeting at Imperial College in London where Nina had introduced us. Now in the sweet summer winds of the South African coast my cell phone rang. I answered, South African style: 'Hello?', 'Hallo, hier ist Alexander.' ('This is Alexander.'). A hippo raised its head up high, letting out a humongous snort. 'Welcher Alexander?' ('Which Alexander?'). Not a good start to any good professional relationship, you would think.

But I spent the best time at ABB under the guidance of Alexander Horch, who has been continuously and without fail supportive of all my endeavours until this very day. He submitted the (successful) application for the NAMUR prize for my PhD thesis, and he let me travel to London on his behalf to regularly attend the CPSE meetings, allowing me to stay in touch with Nina. He also sent me to the strangest of all events, the annual meeting of German control engineers in Boppard. That's a story for another day.

Alexander himself kept up a close collaboration with Nina until his move to a more managerial role as department head. And even after his departure from academia he remains within the control community and was one of the first persons to submit his own contribution to this Festschrift.

At DECRC, I enjoyed working with exceptional, close collaborators of Nina's. Martin Hollender, the brain behind ABB's alarm management solutions and author of the guiding book 'Collaborative Process Automation Systems'. Martin has the uncanny ability to let you talk on about a research question while he remains silent. When you are finished, he will tell you the carefully thought out solution that miraculously developed in his head while you were clueless rambling on.

I learnt that scheduling and control CAN work together by sharing an office with Iiro Harjunkoski for three years¹. Although I did learn to appreciate optimisation after attending a workshop at Carnegie Mellon University by Ignacio Grossman, Iiro's postdoc supervisor and mentor, I would like to point out that none of the optimisation conferences and workshops I attended had a dance floor and are therefore clearly inferior.

Moncef Chioua has been a constant collaborator over the past ten years of Nina's career. He is notoriously undervalued, maybe because he has the ability to become pig headedly stubborn – just because he is irritatingly right. Moncef is loyal, realistic and has the best sense of humour a control engineer can possibly exhibit. His close affinity to Nina is best explained by the fact that there is no one better suited for a heated argument on principal component analysis.

Besides the colleagues within ABB, there is a community of professors in Germany who stem from the ABB Corporate Research Centre in Ladenburg. Amongst them are Nina's collaborators: Alexander Fay at the Helmut Schmidt University in Hamburg, Rainer Drath and Guido Sand, who are now both at the University of Applied Sciences in Pforzheim.

Nina has maintained strong bonds with ABB Norway, Germany and Poland. Also, you can't mention Nina and ABB without also thinking of Alf Isaksson. Or can you? The global roles Alf held within ABB always meant that he is thinly spread and continuously on the move. I met Alf at the IFAC World Congress in Cape Town in 2014. Or didn't I? His presence is fluid: you blink, Alf is there, you blink again, he is gone. You know he definitely exists because he will answer his emails, even when it comes from an academic, ex-ABBler at the other end of the world. And he is one of Nina's biggest supporters and fans.

7. NEW ADVENTURES

I started out saying that I was lucky. I had the great fortune of studying towards my PhD with Nina and this at a time when she had already conducted some of her important work but had not yet moved to Imperial College. I was Nina's only PhD student throughout my time, joined only in my last year by Lamia Benabbas, who worked as a postdoc with Nina at UCL and with ABB Norway. And like all of her students I got to experience her professionalism, dedication, commitment, encouragement and kindness.

I have taken a piece of Nina to wherever I have worked since, to ABB Corporate Research in Ladenburg and to the University of Pretoria. When I have a new piece of research I ask the questions that I think Nina would ask. Her way of explaining difficult context one step at a time together with her lecture notes guide me through my own lectures. I try to model my behaviour on hers when I supervise my own students. When I become too involved I try and step back, being polite but firm. The thought of her integrity makes me

blush and stop when I catch myself gossiping in a professional environment. And my facial expressions are retrained as much as genetically possible.

I wish Nina all the best for her retirement and would like to pass on the note that the ABB colleague, Kevin Starr, wrote in the copy of his book on single loop control methods: "Stay in Control". With all my heart I thank Nina for a brilliant start to my career as a control engineer.

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¹ Shobrys, D. E., & White, D. C. (2002). Planning, scheduling and control systems: why cannot they work together. *Computers & Chemical Engineering*, 26(2), 149-160.

Fig. 1. “Should it stay or should it go?” Joint IChemE, IAM and IET Workshop organised by Nina in London, 31st January 2007. Nina’s knack to always put a date on her slides in legible form made it possible to identify this event exactly.

Fig. 2. Nina at the same workshop in 2007.

Fig. 3. In January 2010, Nina was on her way through Frankfurt from ABB Poland and welcomed my daughter Leah into this world. Leah was a terribly niggly baby – but you can see how Nina’s calmness also worked on her.